

CONSUMERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS GREEN MARKETING AT TIRUCHIRAPPALLI, TAMIL NADU, INDIA

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Abstract

It is the need of the hour that we have to opt the greenish environment as this world is being in the state of Global Warming. We are being forced to move to the situation of Cooling the environment, Ecological environment, Environmental marketing or Green Marketing. The world itself asks us to follow the Green Marketing in whatever we are producing and whatever we are selling. This same thing is also followed in the Tamil Nadu Government saying that **“Let us Carry a Bag and not a Carry Bag”**. Yes, now we are in this situation to save the environment for our future generation. So whatever we try to do, in that we must follow the greenish and we must implement it in our day today activities. In this paper we attempt to introduce the terms and concepts of green marketing, importance of green marketing, examine some of the reason that organizations are adopting a green marketing philosophy and mention some of the problems with green marketing. This study has been done Tiruchirappalli. Both the primary and secondary data were collected for this study. For this study 150 questionnaires were found usable. Hence the exact size of the study is 150. Data analysis has been done by using average and percentages. Through findings we found that ultimately green marketing requires that consumers want a cleaner environment and are willing to pay for it, possibly through higher priced goods, modified individual lifestyles, or even governmental intervention.

Keywords: Global Warming, Green Marketing, Ecological Environment, Cleaner Environment Government Intervention.

INTRODUCTION

“Green Marketing is Need of the Hour”. Yes rapidly changing environment is now a major concern for the people throughout the world, making them more and more concerned about the environment. The quote “Save the Planet, Not Shave the Planet” is now need of the time. To have a sustainable, pollution free environment, it is paramount to implement the concept of green marketing, so that people are educated in this regards as much as possible. Now the question arises What is green marketing? According to the American marketing association, “Green marketing is the marketing of product that are presumed to be environmentally safe thus green marketing incorporates a broad range of activities, including product modification, changes to the production process, packaging changes as well as modifying advertising.” Thus we are going to concentrate on the terms and concepts of green marketing, importance of green marketing, examine some of the reason that organizations are adopting a green marketing philosophy and mention some of the problems with green marketing.

PRESENT TRENDS IN GREEN MARKETING IN INDIA

Organizations are Perceive Environmental marketing as an Opportunity to achieve its objectives. Firms have realized that consumers prefer products that do not harm the natural environment as also the human health. Firms marketing such green products are preferred over the others not doing so and thus develop a competitive advantage, simultaneously meeting their business objectives. Organizations believe they have a moral obligation to be more socially responsible. This is in keeping with the philosophy of CSR which has been successfully adopted by many business houses to improve their corporate image.

THE FUTURE OF GREEN MARKETING

There are many lessons to be learned to avoid green marketing myopia, the short version of all this is that effective green marketing requires applying good marketing principles to make green products desirable for consumers. The question that remains, however, is, what is green marketing's future? Business scholars have viewed it as a “fringe” topic, given that environmentalism's acceptance of limits and conservation does not mesh well with marketing's traditional axioms of “give customer what they want” and “sell as much as you can”. Evidence indicates that successful green products have avoided green marketing myopia by following three important principles:

- 1) Consumer value positioning
- 2) Calibration of consumer knowledge
- 3) Credibility of product claim

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The literature has been reviewed from the reputed journals of both National and International, pertaining to Green Marketing and its related issues. Also the literature has been reviewed from Text Books, Magazines, & Websites.

Murugesan (2008) underlined that firms can use green marketing as an attempt to address cost or profit related issues. Disposing of environmentally harmful by-products, such as polychlorinated biphenyl contaminated oil are becoming increasingly costly and the firms that can reduce harmful wastes can incur substantial cost savings.

Anup Sinha & Jamie Gilpin (2009) primarily focused on finding inefficiencies in the carbon value chain of energy production using renewable methods. By utilizing anaerobic digestion and gasification technology Aura could produce biogas from cattle, swine, and other farm animals.

Dileep Kumar (2010) analysed that how far the hotel business organizations in the tourism sector meet the customer's needs through green marketing effort and how they influence the consumer behaviour and their satisfaction by inducing environmentally responsible behaviour.

Moloy Ghoshal (2011) examined that green marketing was still in infancy. In the perception of marketing scholars, green marketing refers to eco-level and market segmentation and the role of structural factors and economic incentives in influencing

consumer behaviour. The green marketers must understand to satisfy two objectives: improved environmental quality and customer satisfaction.

Ann Kronrod et al (2012) highlighted and explained the surprising prevalence of assertive environmental messages in the media. Environmental agencies, which are populated with people who perceive protecting the environment as a highly important issue, should understand that not all consumers are as informed and concerned about the environment.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The present study about the consumer attitude towards green marketing will bring about the problems and prospects of consumer in green marketing. Most of the consumers are willing to use green marketing products. The standard of living of consumers in Tiruchirappalli is comparatively low. In this study, the researcher aims at findings solutions to the above problems of consumers in green marketing products.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To understand the awareness of consumers towards green marketing.
2. To assess the attitude of consumers towards green branding.
3. To explore awareness level of people of Tiruchirappalli region about green marketing in respect of product and services.
4. To analyze the attitude of consumers for green products.
5. To suggest and recommend how green marketing initiatives can be made successful for government, industry and consumers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher has used structured questionnaire and a five point balanced liker scale for measuring consumer attitude towards green marketing and green branding. The study was undertaken at Tiruchirappalli. Both the primary and secondary data were collected for this study.

a) Primary Sources of Data:

The primary data were collected from the respondents of Tiruchirappalli through a questionnaire designed for a sample of 150 respondents by using the direct questionnaire method.

b) Secondary sources of Data:

The secondary data were collected from books, Journals, Magazines, Newspapers, Reports, Websites and other supplementary sources.

c) Sample Design:

A random sampling method was adopted by the researcher and selected the samples from Tiruchirappalli region representing both genders, different age groups, education level, and monthly income. A well framed questionnaire was circulated among the customers. Totally 175 questionnaires were circulated among them; and only 160 were returned the filled in questionnaire. Out of this, 150 questionnaires were found usable for the study. Hence the exact size of the study is 150.

d) Analysis of data:

The researcher has analysed the collected data with the help of average and percentages. The data from collected respondents are coded, tabulated and analysed into logical statement.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Occupational Status of Consumers

Occupational Status	Number of consumers	Percentage
a) Business	40	27%
b) Employed	110	73%
Total	150	100%

Occupation of respondents will also determine the green marketing of consumers. From the above table it is found that 27 % of the consumers are having business; and 73% of the consumers are employed. It is concluded that the most of the consumers are employed.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Educational Status

Educational status	Number of consumers	Percentage
a)School level	40	27%
b)Under Graduate	60	40%
C)Post-Graduate	30	20%
d)Professional	20	13%
Total	150	100%

Educational qualification is an index of social status. Education is not only basis for acquire knowledge but also getting livelihood. From the above tale it is found that 27% of consumers studied at School level; 40% of consumers studied up to under graduate; 20% of consumers studied up to post graduate; and 13% of consumers studied up to professional level. It is concluded that most of the consumers have studied up to undergraduate education.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Monthly Income

Monthly income	Numbers of consumers	Percentage
a)Less than Rs.5000	40	27%
b)Rs.5001 to Rs.10000	60	40%
c)Rs.10001 to Rs.20000	30	20%
d) More than Rs 20000	20	13%
Total	150	100%

The level of income determines the level of green marketing of consumers. From the above table it shown that 27% of the of consumers earn less than Rs.5000 ;40% of the of consumers earn Rs 5001to10000; 20% of the consumers earn Rs.10001to Rs.20000;and 13% of the consumers earn more than Rs.20000.Therefore, it is examined from the study that majority of the respondents are earning monthly income of RS,5001 to 10000.

Table 4: Consumers believe in the Concept of Green Marketing

Rating scale	No. of. consumers	Percentage
Strongly Agree	89	59%
Agree	42	28%
Neither Disagree Nor agree	8	5.3%
Disagree	9	6%
Strongly Disagree	2	1.7%
Total	150	100%

From the above table it is found that 59% consumers are Strongly Agree; 28% consumers Agree; 5.3% consumers Neither Disagree Nor agree; 6% consumers Disagree; and 1.7 % consumers Strongly Disagree about the concept of green marketing. Most of the consumers strongly agree believe in the concept of green marketing.

Table 5: Awareness of Companies Going Green

Rating scale	No. of. consumers	Percentage
Strongly Agree	90	60%
Agree	25	16%
Neither Disagree Nor agree	15	10%
Disagree	10	7%
Strongly Disagree	10	7%
Total	150	100%

From the above table it is found that 60% consumers Strongly Agree; 16% consumers Agree; 10% consumers Neither Disagree Nor agree; 7% consumers Disagree; and 7 % consumers Strongly Disagree that they are aware of companies going green. Majority of the consumers strongly agree that they are aware of companies going green.

Table 6: Difficulties to Implement Green Marketing concept

Rating scale	No. of. consumers	Percentage
Strongly Agree	100	67%
Agree	34	22%
Neither Disagree Nor agree	10	7%
Disagree	6	4%
Strongly Disagree	-	-
Total	150	100%

From the above table it is found that 67% consumers Strongly Agree; 22% consumers Agree; 7% consumers Neither Disagree Nor agree; 4% consumers Disagree; that it is difficult for all companies to implement green marketing concept. Majority of the consumers strongly agree with the difficulties to implement green marketing concept.

Table 7: Everyone is Responsible for Successful Green Marketing Concept

Rating scale	No. of. consumers	Percentage
Strongly Agree	95	63%
Agree	38	25%
Neither Disagree Nor agree	10	7.5%
Disagree	4	2.5%
Strongly Disagree	3	2%
Total	150	100%

From the above table it is found that 63% consumers Strongly Agree; 25% consumers Agree; 7.5% consumers Neither Disagree Nor agree; 2.5% consumers Disagree; and 2 % consumers Strongly Disagree that they are responsible for successful green

marketing concept. Most of the consumers strongly agree with the responsibility for successful green marketing concept.

Table 8: Green Marketing is More Effective than Regular Marketing

Rating scale	No. of. consumers	Percentage
Strongly Agree	31	20.5%
Agree	30	20%
Neither Disagree Nor agree	54	36%
Disagree	17	11.5%
Strongly Disagree	18	12%
Total	150	100%

From the above table it is observed that 20.5% consumers Strongly Agree; 20% consumers Agree; 36% consumers Neither Disagree Nor agree; 11.5% consumers Disagree; and 12 % consumers Strongly Disagree that they green marketing is more effective than regular marketing. It is examined that Most of the consumers neither Disagree nor agree that Green marketing is more effective than regular marketing.

Table 9: Realizing the Importance of Green Branding

Rating scale	No. of. Consumers	Percentage
Yes	103	69
No	47	31
Total	150	100

The above table clearly indicates that 69% of the Respondents realize the importance of green branding and 31% of the Respondents do not realize the importance of green branding. It is concluded that most of the consumers realize the importance of green branding.

FINDINGS & CONCLUSION

Green marketing is a tool for protecting the environment for future generation. It is not going to be an easy concept. The firm has to plan and then carry out research to find out how feasible it is going to be. Green marketing has to evolve since it is still at its infancy stage. Adoption of Green marketing may not be easy in the short run, but in the long run it will definitely have a positive impact on the firm. Green Marketing is still in the stage of childhood in the Indian companies. Lots of opportunities are available. Now this is the right time to select Green Marketing globally. It will come with drastic change in the world of business if all nations will make strict rules because green marketing is essential to save world from pollution. From the business point of view because a clever marketer is one who not only convinces the consumer, but also involves the consumer in marketing his product. Ultimately green marketing requires that consumers want a cleaner environment and are willing to pay for it, possibly through higher priced goods, modified individual lifestyles, or even governmental intervention. Until this occurs it will be difficult for firms alone to lead the green marketing revolution. An environmental committed organization may not only produce goods that have reduced their detrimental impact on the environment, they may also be able to pressure their suppliers to behave in a more environmentally responsible fashion. Final consumers and industrial buyers also have the ability to pressure organizations to integrate the environment into their corporate culture and thus ensure all organizations minimize the detrimental environmental impact of their activities.

RERSULT

Green marketing is still in its infancy and a lot of research is to be done on green marketing to fully explore its potential. There are some suggestion that an organizations should implement for catering challenges of green marketing and successful exploitation of green marketing. Consumer needs to be made more aware about the merits of Green products. The consumer needs to be educated and made aware of the environmental threats. It should be made sure that the consumer is aware of and concerned about the issues that the product attempts to address. Green Marketing campaign and green advertising is good step towards it. Consumers must be motivated to switch brands or even pay a premium for the greener alternative.

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